

Teacher's Guide for Core Place Value Concepts: Teaching Strategies and Recommended Resources.

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1. Introduction

Alongside the cardinal concept of numbers, and the part-whole concept, the concept of place value is recognised as a critical component in the development of number understanding for children.

Our number system is based on five principles: the principle of bundling and unbundling; the decimal system; the principle of place value; the multiplicative principle; and the additive principle. Teachers require a complete understanding of the concept of place value, and how to teach the concept, as well as appropriate working materials (e.g., MABs, place value charts, place value apps) to assist children in developing a robust understanding of place value. Although the five principles apply regardless of the base being used, in this guide we will only refer to work with students using Base Ten.

The structure of this guide follows a similar pattern for each of the topics and includes a definition, a selection of (some) appropriate representations, possible misconceptions, and how to correct them. Each of the sections are accompanied by explanations and worked examples; however, feel free to customise these examples to suit your learning context.

We hope this guide is useful in supporting your teaching of place value.

2. The decimal part-whole concept

Before working on this concept children should...

- understand the cardinal concept of numbers,
- understand the part-whole concept for natural numbers, and
- know the initial bundle units that are the powers of ten (Ones, Tens, Hundreds...).

Definition

The part-whole concept is the understanding that a whole can be partitioned into parts and, the amount of the whole is the sum of the parts.

The decimal part-whole concept is the understanding that

- a whole can be partitioned into parts that are all multiples of the same power of ten. Recall that the powers of ten include:
 - $1 = 10^0$
 - $10 = 10^1$
 - $100 = 10^2$
 - $1000 = 10^3$
- the amount of the whole is the sum of the amounts of parts (multiples of powers of ten).

Explanation

For example, 6 can be partitioned into $4 + 2$ or $3 + 1 + 2$ or $2 + 2 + 2$.

The decimal part-whole concept is a subconcept of the part-whole concept, where the parts have a special size, namely, a multiple of the same power of ten.

For example, 234 can be partitioned into $200 + 30 + 4$.

Also $200 + 30 + 4$ can be added to 234.

Why is this important?

The decimal part-whole concept is the basis on which further mathematics builds, for example:

- In the symbolic representation of a number, the *value of each of the digits* can be seen when one partitions the whole into the parts that are all multiples of the same power of ten.
- In the symbolic representation of a number, the *value of the number* can be seen when all parts are added together to the whole.
- This is important for *calculating*.

- One needs to partition the number into its multiples of powers of ten.
- After adding the multiples of the powers of ten separately, one needs to add the parts again to determine the *value of the number*.

Explanation

For example, in the number 234,

- the value of the digit 2 is 2×10^2 , that is 200
- the value of the digit 3 is 3×10^1 , that is 30
- the value of the digit 4 is 4×10^0 , that is 4

For example, $200 + 30 + 4 = 234$

For example: $234 + 127$

H	T	O
2	3	4
+ 1	2	7
3	5	11
3	6	1

Step 1. $234 = 2H + 3T + 4O$ $127 = 1H + 2T + 7O$

Step 2. $2H + 1H = 3H$; $3T + 2T = 5T$; $4O + 7O = 11O$
 $3H + 5T + 11O = 3H + 5T + (1T + 10O) = 3H + (5T + 1T) + 10O$
 $= 3H + 6T + 10O = 361$

Using representations with students to support this concept

Appropriate representations used to support the decimal part-whole concept include:

- Part-whole diagrams:

- Base Ten Blocks:

- Expansion cards:

Explanation

In a part-whole diagram, the value of the number is represented in the length of the bars. One can see in the diagram (left) that the whole (234) has the same length as all parts (200 and 30 and 4) added together.

Using Base Ten Blocks, one can see the size of the bundles in the volume of the blocks. By sorting them according to the value of the bundle, one divides the whole into parts that are each the same power of ten, (i.e., 2×10^2 , 3×10^1 , 4×10^0).

Unfolding the expansion card, one can see the value of the place of each digit. In this way, one can partition the whole into parts that are each the same power of ten and add the parts together again to show the whole.

Misconceptions

Possible misconceptions may be:

- Without understanding of place value, children may write $200 + 30 + 4$ as 200304.

How to help

- Show the children that the digit at each place of a number tells the quantity of these special bundle units (powers of ten).

- Children tend to view 234 as $200 + 30 + 4$ without seeing the significance of the 2 as counts of hundreds (2×100) and the 3 as counts of ten (3×10) and the 4 as counts of ones (4×1).

H	T	O
2	3	4

$4O = 4 \times 1 = 4$
 $3T = 3 \times 10 = 30$
 $2H = 2 \times 100 = 200$

H	T	O

- Show the children that each place of a digit in a number has its special value. For example, as 30 is 3×10 , the 3 must be written in the tens place.

3. The concepts of (un-)grouping and (un-)bundling

Before working on this concept children should...

- understand the cardinal concept of numbers,
- understand the decimal part-whole concept for numbers, and
- be able to form different group sizes to skip count, for example, by 2, by 5 and especially for decimal part-whole, by ten.

Definition

The concepts of (un-)grouping and of (un-)bundling are closely connected.

- The concept of bundling objects is the understanding that an amount of objects is first grouped and then labelled. This means that the new group is recognised as a new object with a new name. Once we label the group of objects using a new name, we have bundled the objects. For example, a group of ten ones becomes bundled as one ten.
- The concept of unbundling objects is the inverse operation, which means that a named bundle of objects can also be interpreted as individual objects.

- There are different possibilities to bundle (in the sense of repeating the bundling)
- The different possibilities to bundle are all equivalent to each other in the terms of the total amount (application of the decimal part-whole concept).

Explanation

- For example, 24O is the same as 1T 14O is the same as 2T 4O.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The bundling can be repeated (in the sense of bundling bundles). • If there is no more bundling possible, we call it <i>maximal bundling</i>. This occurs when it is no longer possible to create any further bundles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is also possible to bundle Tens into Hundreds and Hundreds into Thousands and so on. • For example, 24 objects are maximally bundled when represented as 2 Tens and 4 Ones (2T 4O).
<p>Why is this important?</p> <p>As the number of objects to be counted becomes larger, the probability of miscounting increases, as it is easy to count objects twice, or to skip objects. Grouping / bundling helps children to count correctly.</p> <p>The concept of bundling is vital for the subconcept of <i>positional notation</i> (discussed in a later section).</p>	<p>Explanation</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Counting groups and single Ones: „One Ten, two Tens, and one, two, three, four Ones, twenty-four“</p> </div> </div>
<p>Using representations with students to support this concept</p> <p>Appropriate representations used to support the (un-)bundling / (un-)grouping concept include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sticks: to experience the concept of grouping and bundling, one can collect sticks and always tie ten together with a cord. • ice cream sticks are also suitable to group and bundle and are easier to handle than sticks. • Base Ten Blocks: Later in the teaching sequence, Base Ten Blocks can be used, particularly when representing larger numbers. 	<p>Explanation</p> <p>Regardless of the material used, it is important that there are always ten grouped/bundled together and ungrouped/unbundled.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p>To move from grouping to bundling, it is necessary to give the group a new name. The children need to know that one group of ten objects equals one Ten ($10O = 1T$), that is, 1T represents the same amount as 10O.</p>

Misconceptions	How to help
<p>Possible misconceptions may be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The children don't know that the 1T equals 10O. ● Children may not understand that there are different possibilities to bundle, and that they are all equivalent to each other. ● Children may not understand that the principle of bundling is always the same, regardless as to whether 10 Ones are bundled as 1 Ten, 10 Tens as 1 Hundred, and so on. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Let the children work with materials (see representations) and talk aloud, for example, "Now we call this group of ten single sticks one Ten" and write "$10O = 1T$". ● Let the children experience different possibilities to bundle with materials and to record their experiences symbolically, for example, $24 = 24O = 2T\ 4O = 1T\ 14O$. ● Once children are confident in grouping and bundling with Ones and Tens, continue with grouping and bundling with Hundreds and so on.

4. Flexible understanding of Place Value

Before working on this concept children should...

- understand the concept of (un-)grouping, and
- understand the concept of (un-)bundling

Definition

The flexible understanding of place value is the ability to change the partitioning of a number between...

- standard partitioning,
 - strong nonstandard partitioning, and
 - weak nonstandard partitioning.
- *Standard partitioning* is the representation of a number where each part is a multiple of powers of ten that are maximally bundled (see top of figure to the right).
 - *Strong nonstandard partitioning* occurs where some bundle sizes are unbundled completely (see bottom left of figure to the right). This means that in the strong nonstandard partitioning you can always “see” the original digits in the representation.
 - *Weak nonstandard partitioning* occurs where we no longer “see” all of the original digits in the representation (see bottom right of figure to the right).

In each of these partitioning examples, the role of zero indicates the lack of a place rather than indicating none of an amount in terms of cardinality.

Explanation

The figure below demonstrates standard, strong nonstandard, and weak nonstandard partitioning for the number 16 832.

It is important to convey to children that there is only one standard partitioning for any given number. However, there are always different nonstandard partitionings for any given number.

For example, in the number 802 the zero indicates that we have no tens; however, we still have 802 objects in total.

	H	T	O			H	T	O	
	7	9	2	/	3	=	2	6	4
-	6				x3				
	1	9							
-	1	8			x3				
		1	2						
		1	2		x3				
			0						

7H / 3 = 2H rem 1H,
because 2H x 3 = 6H

19T / 3 = 6T rem 1T,
because 6T x 3 = 18T

12O / 3 = 4O,
because 4O x 3 = 12O

Using representations with students to support this concept

Appropriate representations used to support a flexible understanding of place value include:

- Expansion Card:

- Base Ten Blocks:

Explanation

- Unfolding the expansion card, one can initially see the value of the place of each digit. However, the expansion card can also be folded and used to show the *strong nonstandard partitioning*.

For example:

- 2 Hundreds, 3 Tens, and 6 Ones (1st row) is the same as
- 2 Hundreds and 36 Ones (2nd row) or
- 23 Tens and 6 Ones (3rd row) or
- 236 Ones (4th row)

- Using Base Ten Blocks, children can experiment with representing the same amount in many ways. For example, in the picture left, the number 236 is shown in four different ways (from left to right)
 - 2 Hundreds, 3 Tens, and 6 Ones

- Place Value Chart App

- Standard representation of 181 (1H 8T 1O)

- Weak non-standard representation of 181 (1H 7T 11O)

- 2 Hundreds and 36 Ones
- 23 Tens and 6 Ones
- 236 Ones

Children can then be challenged to demonstrate other combinations to represent 236, for example 1 Hundred, 13 Tens and 6 Ones.

- Using the Place Value Chart App, it is easy to demonstrate how 181 (1H 8T 1O) can be represented in
 - the standard partitioning representation
 - a weak nonstandard partitioning representation (1H 7T 11O) or
 - a strong nonstandard partitioning (18T 1O)

Children can then be challenged to demonstrate other combinations to represent 181 using strong or weak nonstandard partitioning.

- Strong non-standard representation of 181 (18T 1O)

Misconceptions

Possible student misconceptions may be:

- Children may think that standard and non-standard partitionings represent different amounts rather than different representations of the same amount.
- Children may think that we can only have a maximum of nine of any place.
- Role of zero:
Children might misunderstand zero's role in positional notation. They may think that the zero in numbers represents

How to help

- Use the Place Value Chart App and demonstrate to children that dragging one token from the Tens to the Ones, does not change the total number (1H 8T 1O), but only how it is represented (1H 7T 11O).
- To confirm this, drag one token from the Ones place back to the Tens place to change (1H 7T 11O) back to the standard representation of (1H 8T 1O). The same example can be demonstrated with Base Ten Blocks, where one of the Tens blocks can be unbundled into ten Ones blocks.
- This is correct, if we want to represent a number without using a Place Value chart. However, if we use the Place Value chart, it is possible to have more than nine at a place. Activities such as those above reinforce that symbolically it is sometimes necessary to record a number greater than nine.
- Clarify that zero signifies the absence of a bundle in that place. Compare examples of number representations where the zero is not needed, (e.g., when using a Place Value chart, writing number words, or noting bundling units) with representations

nothing and is therefore not required. Thus, they may write 5H 3O as “53” instead of “503”.

where it is necessary, (e.g., when writing the number using positional notation).

Examples of number representations where zero is not needed:

The image shows three examples of number representations without a zero. On the left, two small white cards with black text are shown: one with '3O' and one with '5H'. In the middle, a speech bubble contains the text 'five-hundred-and-three'. On the right, a 2x3 grid represents a place value chart with columns labeled 'H', 'T', and 'O'. The bottom row contains the digits '5', an empty space, and '3'.

Example of number representation where zero is needed:
When writing a number using digits, for example, 503 - the zero signifies the absence of bundles of Tens in positional notation. To help children, use step-by-step examples showing the transition from amounts represented in Place Value charts to fully bundled numbers with zero

H	T	O
5		3

The digit “0” must be added to write the amount without using a place-value-chart to signify the absence of bundles of Tens:

H	T	O
5	0	3

The amount can then be written as “503” using positional notation.

5. The subconcept of positional notation

The sub concept of positional notation consists of understanding the requirement for maximal bundling, the value of digit, and the value of number. These ideas are further explained in the two subchapters below.

Before working on this concept children should...

- understand the decimal part-whole concept.
- be able to (un-)group and (un-)bundle amounts.
- know the initial bundling units of the decimal system (Ones, Tens, Hundreds...).
- be able to maximally bundle (in the decimal system).

5.1 Requirement for maximal bundling in positional notation

<p>Definition Positional notation requires maximal bundling.</p>	<p>Explanation For example, the amount in the Place Value chart below is not maximally bundled, as further bundling is still possible. Without maximal bundling, the number cannot be written without the Place Value chart (because it would then be 7142).</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1406 943 1765 1007"><tr><td>H</td><td>T</td><td>O</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>1</td><td>42</td></tr></table> <p>Maximal bundling occurs when the 42 ones are bundled into 4 Tens, leaving 2 Ones, and those 4 Tens are added to the existing 1 Ten.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1406 1155 1765 1219"><tr><td>H</td><td>T</td><td>O</td></tr><tr><td>7</td><td>5</td><td>2</td></tr></table> <p>Maximal bundling results in only one digit per place. Thus, the number can only be correctly written as “752” (without using a Place Value chart).</p>	H	T	O	7	1	42	H	T	O	7	5	2
H	T	O											
7	1	42											
H	T	O											
7	5	2											

Why is maximal bundling important?

- Clear and unambiguous representation:
Maximal bundling ensures a clear representation of a number without needing a Place Value chart. Each digit represents the amount in its respective place value.

Explanation

For example, 752 can be represented in various ways when using a Place Value chart e.g.,

H	T	O
6	15	2
5	25	2
7	4	12

However, if we were to record the numbers without knowing their position in the chart (e.g., 6152, 5252, 7412), this would incorrectly represent the overall amount (i.e., 752).

Therefore, the total amount is only clearly represented after maximal bundling (i.e., each digit in the number stands for the number of bundles according to the places of the digits [positional notation])

H	T	O
7	5	2

When maximally bundling 752, the amount must be represented in the chart as 7H 5T 2O and written as “752”.

Using representations with students to support this concept

Appropriate representations used to support maximal bundling in positional notation include:

- Place Value Chart App

Explanation

- The app can be used to improve understanding of the requirement for maximal bundling, as it visually indicates when bundling is still possible by highlighting, in red, amounts greater than 9 in the column headings.

	<p>The 12 Ones (written in red) indicate that further bundling is possible.</p>
<p>Misconceptions</p> <p>Possible misconceptions may be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children may misunderstand when maximal bundling is necessary. They may struggle with switching between representations where positional notation is required and those where it is not. 	<p>How to help</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Let children convert one representation that does not use positional notation (i.e., where amounts are represented in nonstandard ways) into one that does require it. For example, using bundle units, the amount 2T 14O should be converted into the corresponding number using positional notation. The Place Value Chart may help with the transition.

5.2 Value of digit and value of number

<p>Definition</p> <p>The value of a digit at a place is the product of the digit and the value of its place.</p>	<p>Explanation</p> <p>For example, in the number 752,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the digit 7 is in the Hundreds place, so its value is $7 \times 100 = 700$ the digit 5 is in the Tens place, so its value is $5 \times 10 = 50$ the digit 2 is in the Ones place, so its value is $2 \times 1 = 2$
---	--

<p>The value of a number is the sum of the values of the digits (application of the decimal part-whole concept).</p>	<p>The value of a digit can also be found by unbundling all bundles of the according place into single ones, for example 7H can be unbundled into 700O.</p> <p>For example, the value of the number 752 can be found by adding the value of its digits:</p> $752 = (7 \times 100) + (5 \times 10) + (2 \times 1) = 700 + 50 + 2$ <p>The value of the number "752" represents the whole, which is composed of the values of its individual digits (parts).</p>
<p>Why are the value of digit and the value of number important?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Efficient representation: Positional notation allows for efficient representation of numbers, even large ones, using only 10 digits (0 to 9). ● Understanding the magnitudes of numbers: Positional notation (value of digit and value of number) supports the decimal part-whole-concept, as children should understand digits as parts of a number, that are of the same powers of ten and the whole number as the sum of the amount of the parts. This concept is crucial for grasping the real size of numbers and is fundamental for calculations, as it helps break down numbers into parts (digits) and understand their combined value (see section on decimal part-whole). 	<p>Explanation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● For example, in “752”, the 7 in the Hundreds place makes it much larger than “257”, where the 7 is in the One’s place. Even though the same digits are used, the value of the digit changes depending on their position, and thus the overall amount changes as well.
<p>Using representations with students to support this concept Appropriate representations used to support the value of digit and value of number are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Place Value Chart App 	<p>Explanation</p> <p><i>Value of digit:</i> unbundling all bundles of a digit’s place into single ones:</p>

For the number “700”, the value of the digit 7 can be seen by unbundling the 7 Hundreds into 700 Ones.

Value of place: unbundling all bundles at all places into single Ones:

For the number “752”, the value of the number can be seen by unbundling the 5 Tens into 50 Ones and the 7 Hundreds into 700 Ones.

Value of digit: Unfolding the expansion card, the value of place of each digit can be seen.

- Expansion Card:

Misconceptions

Possible misconceptions may be:

- While using a Place Value chart, there can be 2 Tens and 14 Ones; however, for positional notation, the Ones must first be maximally bundled. Children might write the number as “214” as they don’t understand the need for maximal bundling in positional notation.

How to help

T	O
2	14

After maximal bundling.

T	O
3	4

The number must be written as “34” when using positional notation.

The Place Value Chart App may help as well, as it connects different representations of an amount that require no positional notation (place value chart, number word) with representations that do require positional notation (number)

6. The importance of Place Value regarding the operations

Before working on this concept children should...

- understand the cardinal concept of numbers,
- understand the (decimal) part-whole concept for numbers,
- know the initial bundle units that are the powers of ten (Ones, Tens, Hundreds...), and
- have a flexible understanding of Place Value.

6.1 Addition and Subtraction

Definition

Mathematically, addition is the union of non-elementary (disjunctive) quantities. Embedded in contexts, addition can be interpreted as uniting, balancing, or comparing quantities.

The subtraction of numbers is the difference quantity of two quantities and is the inverse operation of addition. Embedded in contexts, subtraction can be interpreted as take away, difference, or missing addend.

Explanation

For example, if one unites a quantity of 5 objects and a quantity of (different) 3 objects, there are 8 objects altogether:
 $5 + 3 = 8$

For example, if one has a quantity of 8 objects and takes away a quantity of 3 objects, 5 objects remain as the difference quantity:
 $8 - 3 = 5$

The part-whole concept is the basis for addition and subtraction, as a whole is the sum of the parts:

$$W = P_1 + P_2; \quad P_1 + P_2 = W$$

$$W = P_2 + P_1; \quad P_2 + P_1 = W$$

and if you subtract one part from the whole, one gets the other part:

$$P_2 = W - P_1; \quad W - P_1 = P_2$$

$$P_1 = W - P_2; \quad W - P_2 = P_1$$

$$14 = 10 + 4 \quad 10 + 4 = 14$$

$$14 = 4 + 10 \quad 4 + 10 = 14$$

$$4 = 14 - 10 \quad 14 - 10 = 4$$

$$10 = 14 - 4 \quad 14 - 4 = 10$$

Why is PV important for addition and subtraction?

The algorithms for addition and subtraction are both based on an understanding of PV and many of the strategies used to solve addition and subtraction tasks also require an understanding of PV:

- Partition into Tens and Ones and recombine

Explanation

For example:

$$25 + 12 = 2\text{T } 5\text{O} + 1\text{T } 2\text{O} = 3\text{T } 7\text{O} = 37$$

$$67 - 14 = 6\text{T } 7\text{O} - 1\text{T } 4\text{O} = 5\text{T } 3\text{O} = 53$$

	T	O
	2	5
+	1	2
	3	7

	T	O
	6	7
-	1	4
	5	3

- Fill up the bundle (also known as “bridging through ten”)

For example:

$$6 + 7 = 6 + 4 + 3 = 10 + 3 = 13$$

$$6\text{O} + 4\text{O} = 10\text{O} = 1\text{T}$$

		$6\text{O} + 7\text{O} = \underline{\quad}$					
1.		$6\text{O} + \underline{\quad} = 10\text{O} = 1\text{T}$	<table border="1"><tr><td>T</td><td>O</td></tr><tr><td></td><td>10</td></tr></table>	T	O		10
T	O						
	10						
		$6\text{O} + 4\text{O} = 10\text{O} = 1\text{T}$	<table border="1"><tr><td>T</td><td>O</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td></td></tr></table>	T	O	1	
T	O						
1							
2.		$7\text{O} - 4\text{O} = 3\text{O}$	<table border="1"><tr><td>7</td></tr><tr><td>3</td><td>4</td></tr></table>	7	3	4	
7							
3	4						
3.		$1\text{T} + 3\text{O}$	<table border="1"><tr><td>T</td><td>O</td></tr><tr><td>1</td><td>3</td></tr></table>	T	O	1	3
T	O						
1	3						

- Analogy: If you do not need to go “bridge through ten”, then you can add/subtract in each Ten in the same way.

- Analogy: In each place (bundle unit), you can add/subtract in the same way.

For example:

$$3 + 4 = 7, \text{ that is why } 53 + 4 = 57$$

$$6 - 2 = 4, \text{ that is why } 36 - 2 = 34$$

	T	O
	5	3
+		4
	5	7

	T	O
	3	6
-		2
	3	4

For example:

$$3 + 4 = 7, \text{ that is why } 30 + 40 = 70 \text{ (} 3T + 4T = 7T \text{)}$$

$$6 - 2 = 4, \text{ that is why } 60 - 20 = 40 \text{ (} 6T - 2T = 4T \text{)}$$

	T	O
		3
+		4
		7

	T	O
		6
-		2
		4

	T	O
	3	0
+	4	0
	7	0

	T	O
	6	0
-	2	0
	4	0

Using representations with students to support this concept

Appropriate representations used to support addition and subtraction include:

- Base Ten Blocks

Explanation

For example:

$$25 + 12 = 2T \ 5O + 1T \ 2O = 3T \ 7O = 37$$

- Place Value Chart

For example:

$$60 - 20 = 40, \text{ thus } 6T - 2T = 4T \text{ (} 60 - 20 = 40 \text{)}$$

T	O
	● ● ● ● ● ●

T	O
● ● ● ● ● ●	

Misconceptions

Possible misconceptions may be:

- The value of a digit at a place is not considered in the "Partition into Tens and Ones and recombine" strategy, so Tens and Ones are added together at random. For example, the addition of $34 + 52$ is carried out as follows:
 $3 + 2 = 5$ and $4 + 5 = 9$, which results in $34 + 52 = 59$
- When subtracting, students often swap the order of the digits in the ones place using the "Partition into Tens and Ones and recombine" strategy to be able to use them for numbers that would require bridging through 10. For example, the problem $56 - 29$ is calculated as follows:

How to help

- Demonstrate to the children that the value of the place at which a digit stands is very important. Only digits that are at the same place can be added, as they are bundles of the same size (O, T, ...). Show them the value of the place of the digits in a Place Value chart.
- | T | O |
|---|---|
| 3 | 4 |
| 5 | 2 |
- Demonstrate to the children that subtraction is not commutative. That means that the numbers or digits of the subtrahend (1st number) and the minuend (2nd number) cannot be swapped. One needs to unbundle.

$5T - 2T = 3T$ and $9O - 6O = 3O$, which results in $56 - 29 = 33$.

Show the children a range of strategies to solve this task, for example $(56 - 29 = 56 - 30 + 1)$ or $(56 - 29 = 57 - 30)$.

6.2 Multiplication and Division

Definition

The multiplication of two quantities can be represented as indicated below.

$A \times B$

$|A \times B| = a \times b = 3 \times 4 = 12$

Explanation

For example, if there are 3 objects in one quantity and 4 objects in another quantity, there are $3 \times 4 = 12$ possible pairs in the product.

Division is the inverse operation of multiplication.

As with addition and subtraction, the part-whole concept is the basis for multiplication and division, as the whole is the sum of the parts. The important difference is that in multiplication and division all of the parts must be the same size:

$$W = P + P + P + \dots P = n \times P$$

$$W - P - P - P - \dots P = W / P = n$$

For example,

$$40 = 10 + 10 + 10 + 10$$

$$40 - 10 - 10 - 10 - 10 = 0$$

$$40 = 4 \times 10$$

$$4 \times 10 = 40$$

$$40 = 10 \times 4$$

$$10 \times 4 = 40$$

$$40 = 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4 + 4$$

$$40 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 - 4 = 0$$

$$10 = 40 / 4$$

$$40 / 4 = 10$$

$$4 = 40 / 10$$

$$40 / 10 = 4$$

Why is PV important for multiplication and division?

The algorithms for multiplication and division are both based on an understanding of PV and many of the strategies used to solve multiplication and division tasks also require an understanding of PV:

- Use of the distributive law for multiplication with bigger numbers

Explanation

For example:

$$17 \times 4 = (10 + 7) \times 4 = 10 \times 4 + 7 \times 4 = 40 + 28 = 68$$

One needs to use the Decimal Part-Whole Concept to more easily multiply numbers.

- Use of the distributive law to make dividing easier

For example:

$$369 / 3 = (3H + 6T + 9O) / 3$$

$$= 3H / 3 + 6T / 3 + 9O / 3 = 1H + 2T + 3O = 123$$

H	T	O
3	6	9

Using representations with students to support this concept

An appropriate representation used to support multiplication and division is the

- Place Value chart

Explanation

For example: $12186 \div 6$

In the Place Value chart, you can easily make and see the multiples of 6 in the non-standard partitioning (see below).

$$\begin{aligned} 12186 \div 6 &= (12\text{Th} + 18\text{T} + 6\text{O}) \div 6 \\ &= 12\text{Th} \div 6 + 18\text{T} \div 6 + 6\text{O} \div 6 = 2\text{Th} + 3\text{T} + 1\text{O} = 2031 \end{aligned}$$

TTh	Th	H	T	O
1	2	1	8	6
	12		18	6

Misconceptions

Possible misconceptions may be:

- When multiplying two two-digit numbers, for example 12×13 , children may use the decimal Part-Whole Concept and partition the 12 into $10 + 2$ and the 13 into $10 + 3$, and only multiply 10×10 to 100 and 2×3 to 6. This would lead to the wrong result of $12 \times 13 = 106$.
- When dividing (e.g., $12186 \div 6$) using the non-standard partitioning, children may forget the “0” in the result and calculate $12 \div 6 = 2$, $18 \div 6 = 3$, $6 \div 6 = 1$, so $12186 \div 6 = 231$

How to help

- Use an area (rectangle) representation of the multiplication task and highlight within this rectangle the parts of the multiplication.

- Show the task in the Place Value Chart and use a “0” to represent none of the empty place.

TTh	Th	H	T	O
1	2	1	8	6
	12		18	6

↓ /6

TTh	Th	H	T	O
	2	0	3	1

7. Place Value and decimals

Before working on this concept children should...

- be able to (un)group and (un)bundle amounts,
- know the bundling units of the decimal system (Ones, Tens, Hundreds, etc.), and
- be able to maximally bundle (in the decimal system).

Definition	Explanation
<p>The concept of decimal fractions is the understanding that these numbers can represent amounts between whole numbers. It includes the following sub-components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Decimal fractions are a special type of fraction that represent amounts that are powers of ten smaller than one whole. These amounts are represented in different ways to common fractions.• Place Value extends indefinitely to the right of the Ones place.• The digits to the right of the decimal point represent amounts less than one.• Extends whole number place value relationships to fractional relationships (i.e., the relationship between one place and its neighbour is still 10:1 or 1:10).	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• For example, the amount of one-tenth can be represented as a common fraction ($\frac{1}{10}$) or a decimal fraction (0.1) and the amount of one Fourth can be represented as a common fraction ($\frac{1}{4}$) or as a decimal fraction (0.25).• For example, numbers can be represented that include Tenths, Hundredths, Thousandths ... Millionths ...• For example, in the number 3.14 the 3 represents three Ones while the 1 represents one-tenth and the 4 represents four-hundredths.• For example, in the number 1.11 the 1 furthest left represents one whole, the next 1 represents $\frac{1}{10}$th of 1, and the final 1 (furthest right) represents $\frac{1}{10}$th of $\frac{1}{10}$th (or $\frac{1}{100}$th of one whole).

Why is this important?

Understanding decimal fractions is important because it allows children to ...

- extend their understanding of whole numbers to numbers less than one and to numbers between the whole numbers.
- represent and compare fractional amounts in more transparent ways.
- use numbers in numeracy and scientific contexts.

Explanation

- For example, once children understand the PV relationships in whole numbers - bundling and unbundling, powers of ten etc., then these understandings are directly transferable to decimal fractions.

- When comparing fractions, it is often easier to represent both amounts as decimal fractions. For example, determining which is larger $\frac{6}{8}$ or $\frac{2}{3}$ is easier when they are represented as decimal fractions (0.75 and 0.66) as children can see that $\frac{6}{8}$ represents a greater amount than $\frac{2}{3}$.
- In later years children need to use and represent amounts in numeracy and scientific contexts. For example,
 - Numeracy - working out percentage costs in shopping contexts (25% discount is 0.25 multiplied by initial amount)
 - Expanded notation - where very large and small numbers can be represented simply. For example, the number 13 000 000 can be represented as 13×10^6

Using representations with students to support this concept

Appropriate representations used to support the decimal part-whole concept include:

- Physical representations that show that decimals are a part of a whole. Once the children have experienced decimals with 3-D physical materials, they can use 2-D grids or Decimats such as the one below to represent decimal numbers.

- Example Grids

- Decimats – in the example below the amount of 0.125 is shown.

Explanation

- Children should initially experience that tenths and hundredths are part of one whole - so demonstrate that one bundling stick can be cut into ten tenths and (if possible and carefully) one tenth can be cut into ten hundredths.

They can then use pictorial representations and shade in areas to represent fractional amounts.

Both grids and decimats are useful resources.

- Expansion card:

- Place Value Chart App

- Standard representation of 1.81 (1O 8t 1h)

- Unfolding the expansion card, one can initially see the value of the place of each digit. However, the expansion card can also be folded and used to show the *strong nonstandard partitioning*.

For example:

- 6 Ones, 3 tenths and 6 hundredths is the same as
- 6 Ones and 36 hundredths (2nd row) or
- 63 tenths and 6 hundredths (3rd row) or
- 636 hundredths (4th row).

- Using the Place Value Chart App, it is easy to demonstrate how numbers with fractional parts work the same as whole numbers in terms of the relationships between the places.

For example, 1.81 can be represented in

- the standard partitioning representation (1O 8t 1h) (top);
- a weak nonstandard partitioning representation (1O 7t 11h); or
- a strong nonstandard partitioning (18t 1h).

Children can then be challenged to demonstrate other combinations to represent 1.81 using strong or weak nonstandard partitioning.

- Weak non-standard representation of 1.81 (1H 7t 11h)

- Strong non-standard representation of 1.81 (18t 1h)

Misconceptions

Possible misconceptions may be:

- That the decimal point separates positive and negative numbers.

How to help

- Children may think that the decimal point indicates the separation of positive numbers (numbers greater than zero) and negative numbers (numbers less than zero), whereas the decimal point represents amounts larger than one whole (left of decimal point) and smaller than one whole (right of the decimal point). Using a number line can be helpful in correcting this misconception.

- That the Place Value chart is symmetrical around the decimal point.

- When comparing numbers, the number with the most digits is the larger / largest number.

- Given that there are Tens and Tenths and Hundreds and Hundredths, children may therefore think that there is a “Oneths” and that the Place Value chart is symmetrical around the decimal point. Using a diagram such as this can be helpful in clarifying this misconception.

Thousands						thousandths
	Hundreds				hundredths	
		Tens		tenths		
			Ones			

- In whole numbers, the number with the most digits is always the largest (e.g., a 3-digit number is always larger than any 2-digit numbers). This is not always the case with decimal numbers (e.g., 1.14 is smaller than 1.2). Children need opportunities to represent these amounts using materials such as the grids used above.

8. Language and Place Value

Before working on this concept children should...

- understand the cardinal concept of numbers,
- understand the concepts of (un-)grouping and (un-)bundling, and
- know the initial number words.

Definition

The children can connect the parts of a number word to:

- the respective quantity of bundle units and
- the respective digits in a number symbol.

Explanation

Children may be able to say number words without any understanding of Place Value. However, for Place Value understanding, it is important that they connect the parts of a number word, for example “thirty” and “four” in the number word “thirty-four”, to the quantity of 3 Tens and 4 Ones and to the respective digits in the number symbol “34”.

Why is this important?

In teaching and learning mathematics, language plays an important role. The formation rules for number words differ in each language.

Explanation

For example, the number 235

<p>One rule is “number inversion”, which occurs when the sequence of the values of places from the symbolic representation (left to right) is changed in the verbal and written number word sequences. Whereas the value of each place in positional notation decreases from left to right, in cases of number inversion this rule does not always apply in how word names are constructed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in the German language is (quantity of hundreds) - (quantity of ones) - “und” - (quantity of tens): zweihundert-fünf-und-dreißig • in the English language, 235 is (quantity of hundreds) “and” (quantity of tens) - (quantity of ones): two hundred and thirty-five <p>Number Inversion occurs in the “teens” in many languages,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • for example, the number 15 in German, Afrikaans, and English is spoken as (quantity of ones) –“zehn” / ”tien” / “teen”; fünf-zehn, vyf-tien, or fif-teen respectively.
<p>Using representations with students to support this concept Appropriate representations used to support language and Place Value include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The use of colours to support the connections between the parts of a number word and the according place of the digit in the number 	<p>Explanation</p> <p>For example,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 235: zweihundert-fünf-und-dreißig (the 2 and “zweihundert” are in red; the 5 and the “fünf” are in green; and the 3 and “dreißig” are in blue) • 15: fifteen (the 1 and “teen” are in blue and the 5 and “fif” are in green)
<p>Misconceptions Possible misconceptions may be that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children write “Vier-und-dreißig” / “Thirty-four” incorrectly as “43” by representing the places reading from left to right (as they do when writing the numbers symbolically). 	<p>How to help</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talk with the children about the formation rules of number words, for example that “-ig”, “-tig”, “-ty” are suffixes representing an amount of Tens. • Make the connection to the bundle units clear to the children before writing the number, for example “Vier-und-dreißig, these are three Tens and four Ones”.